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FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION COMPETENCIES

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Abstract: *we consider the student as a subject of management of the process of mastering knowledge on the use of information technologies, and we consider management not as an influence of the teacher on the student, but as an interaction between the teacher and the student. According to our interpretation, management of the process of forming the readiness of the future teacher to use information technologies in professional activities consists in the implementation of the transformation of the student from an object to a subject of management. The formed readiness of a student to use information technologies in their activities is a self-managed activity, so we define the pedagogical conditions under consideration by the teacher and the student at the level of self – management, as the presence of management.*

Keywords: *Information, Telecommunications, traditional education.*

Today, the ability to use information and telecommunications technologies is considered in proportion to the reading and writing skills required for every member of society. In this regard, the knowledge and skills acquired by future specialists in this direction will allow us to determine the ways of development of society in the future. Therefore, informatization of Education requires real changes in the work of teachers by introducing new requirements for their professional qualities and levels of training. Teachers do not need to be specialists in the field of programming, as it is performed by a specialist who has received professional training in accordance with this specialty, but a teacher is required to understand the basics of programming and understand the essence of the programmer's work.

And when implementing such requirements, there is a need to determine the pedagogical conditions for the formation of students' readiness to use information technologies. Modernity is the time of Information Technology. Achievements of scientific and technological progress are widely introduced and used in almost all spheres of our society. The education system does not go beyond the modern trends in society, but uses almost all positive changes in accordance with its purpose and as needed. At the same time, new innovative teaching technologies are being introduced into the education system. The education system is engaged in the preparation of resources that form and develop society, make changes, and therefore must be constantly improved. "I don't know", he said. we are witnessing the implementation of measures. "In the address of the head of State" "New Kazakhstan in the new world" "it is necessary to achieve the provision of high – quality educational services at the level of world standards throughout the country", "the seventh subparagraph of the eighteenth direction of the address reads: "the task is to create specialized educational areas aimed at information technologies and new forms of information dissemination", as well as in the third subparagraph of the seventeenth direction" - it is necessary to develop the practice of online learning and create educational television in the country, it is noted that today the education system needs to be based on new pedagogical technologies and the widespread use of information tools. In the traditional education system, the main goal of professional educational institutions that train

qualified specialists is to master the profession, and now, entering the world educational space, to provide a result – oriented education system based on the competence of a person to prepare a competitive person is one of the most pressing issues at the moment. We consider the student as a subject of management of the process of mastering knowledge on the use of information technologies, and we consider management not as an influence of the teacher on the student, but as an interaction between the teacher and the student. According to our interpretation, management of the process of forming the readiness of the future teacher to use information technologies in professional activities consists in the implementation of the transformation of the student from an object to a subject of management. The formed readiness of a student to use information technologies in their activities is a self-managed activity, so we define the pedagogical conditions under consideration by the teacher and the student at the level of self – management, as the presence of management. In addition, we rely on the following laws: to the extent that external influences correspond to the internal needs of the individual, they are provided with conditions for their self-activity, where the level of self-control of their actions is high. Hence, the teacher faces the following task – to choose the most appropriate management approach to the process of forming students ‘ readiness to use information technologies in professional activities, based on the needs of students, increasing their activity and self-confidence; the following ratio should be observed here: with a large amount of management, the level of activity and independence of students will be low, and with a small amount of management – the level of activity and independence will be high. In this regard, N.D. Nikandrov’s point of view is close to us: “it is possible to master learning in conditions of full management, the purpose of learning is to develop thinking and other qualities of the individual, which requires a reduction in the amount of management, the need to provide students with a greater degree of self – confidence”. The next condition for the formation of the future teacher’s readiness to use information technologies in professional activities is the use of modular technology for providing educational material on the use of information technologies in professional activities. In the course of the study, we considered the problem of finding forms of formation of the future teacher’s readiness to use information technologies in professional activities, which, on the one hand, ensure the individualization of students’ work, on the other hand, the technologization of the process of introducing students into their activities to study the possibilities of using information technologies. Thus, this problem can be solved by applying the capabilities of the modular approach in teaching.

Currently, a modular approach is widely used in pedagogical practice, and its positive impact on the effectiveness of professional training is considered significant. The modular approach is based on the following principles: consistency, structuring, modularity, dynamic, goal counting and feedback, activity and visibility. The modular training system takes the teacher as the central figure of this process, providing opportunities for full achievement of the required results.

Widely used ICT tools in the field of Education:

- interactive whiteboard;
- multimedia;
- Internet space;
- electronic textbook.

For a teacher, an electronic textbook is an open methodological system that is developed on a daily basis. Each teacher can further improve it by adding materials to their teaching practice.

Effectiveness of using a new ICT in the classroom:

- Allows the student to think freely;
- Develops intelligence;

- Increases creative activity;
- Fosters collective action;
- Improves the richness of the language;
- Increases the ability to search in all directions.

As a key tool in supporting education system management, the e-learning system should store all the necessary information about the educational environment. It should also act as a tool for information and scientific and methodological support for the development of Education, secondly, as a tool for monitoring the education system through centralized accumulation of data from any node of the e-learning system, and thirdly, as a decision-making tool that ensures the formation of the necessary statistical data on the education system and reporting on various aspects.

The future of our country and its accession to the ranks of civilized countries are reflected in the image of today's generation. The main task in the field of modern education is the search for effective new methods of introducing innovations into the content of education from the point of view of social and pedagogical organization and the training of teachers who can implement them. It has always been one of the most pressing issues. This creates new requirements for adapting the younger generation to life in accordance with the socio-economic tasks of society. At the present stage, the transition to the national model of Education requires a creative teacher-researcher, thinker teacher who has mastered the latest methods of teaching and upbringing, innovative pedagogical Technologies, is able to adopt psychological and pedagogical Diagnostics, is able to quickly get rid of the old stereotypes that have developed in pedagogical work and is able to build their own path in real practical activities.

The organization of the educational process at the level of the state educational standard requires the introduction of new pedagogical technologies.

Recently, the meaning of the concept of technology has expanded.

For example, in the scientific field of Computer Science, the concept of Information Technology began to appear, in the field of Physiology-the concept of technology of biological systems, and so on.

A. Makarenko, who first introduced the concept of learning technology "to pedagogical science, now this concept is widely used in the educational process. T. Ilina was the first to conduct a systematic study of the concept of pedagogical technology".

According to I. Talyzina, the main goal of pedagogical technology is to identify the most effective methods used in practice to achieve the didactic goal. Pedagogical technology is a system of scientifically based requirements applied in the direction of scientific systematization of the learning process, i.e. in the practice of teaching.

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THE ACTIVITY OF A TEACHER-PSYCHOLOGIST IN MODERN SCHOOLS

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Annotation : *In order to work as a teacher-psychologist at school, a person with a comprehensive education must first understand the profession, have knowledge of the profession and have professional training. This is due to the fact that the pedagogue-psychologist has the ability to communicate with people, the ability to work, the culture of communication, the ability to behave and to communicate with people, the ability to organize, the ability to communicate with people. should. Adolescence is considered a difficult and testing period. Such an assessment depends, first of all, on the many qualitative changes that are taking place at this time.*

Keywords. *Affect, adolescent, school, adolescent, psychological.*

One of the pedagogical and psychological activities of the school is the formation of a favorable microclimate for the mental health of the child, ie for the spiritual, physiological development and the environment. When moving from primary school to 5th grade, the child will have crisis characteristics as he or she adapts to the skills in middle school. Difficulties in middle school

learning, changes in the psyche of the student, difficulties in mastering the emotional sphere, affect academic performance, mental health. Different teachers have different teaching methods, are accustomed to the rules of the school, parents complain about the decline in academic performance, regardless of the age of the child; The manifestation of affective behavior in the child's life, emotional reactions during communication, neurotic stress are observed. One of the objects of the study of ways out of the crisis of the child in the period of adaptation is the family. The microenvironment of the family is a key factor in the development of special, creative abilities of the child's general intelligence.

In order to work as a teacher-psychologist at school, a person with a comprehensive education must first understand the profession, have knowledge of the profession and professional training. This is due to the fact that the pedagogue-psychologist has the ability to communicate with people, the ability to work, the culture of communication, the ability to behave and communicate with people, the ability to organize, the ability to communicate with people. Adolescence is a difficult and testing period. Such an assessment depends, first of all, on the many qualitative changes that are taking place at this time. These changes are sometimes of a nature that radically alters the child's past characteristics, interests and relationships: it can occur in a relatively short period of time, often unexpectedly, and the developmental process can be abruptly intense. Second, the changes taking place in one of the two, on the one hand, are accompanied by various significant subjective difficulties in the adolescent himself, and on the other hand, are accompanied by difficulties in his upbringing. Adolescents do not tolerate the influence of adults. There are various forms of disobedience and protest (stubbornness, rudeness, naughtiness, cowardice, introversion). Socio-psychological issues affect the emergence of manifestations of developmental tests in adolescence.

Such qualities of a person are prerequisites for schooling and upbringing. In our country, school has always received a lot of attention. The purpose of the school is to teach, develop and educate children and adolescents, as well as to address various socio-psychological issues.

It aims to form a socially active person who will bring spiritual wealth, moral purity and physical health. However, in addition to the crises of adolescence, schoolchildren face social and psychological problems.